

New *N*-Glucosides. Syntheses of 1- and 5-Glucosyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets

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Several 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-aryl/alkyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (4) and 1-aryl/(*H*)-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (7) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide with aryl/alkylisothiocyanates and 1-aryl-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides with tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate, respectively.

N-Glucosylated compounds are known for their physiological and pharmaceutical importance¹.

Recently, we have reported several *N*-glucosyl thiocarbamides² (1). Now we report the syntheses of some 1- and 5-glucosylated-2,4-isodithiobiurets.

A free base of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (2) (prepared by the interaction of 1 and benzyl chloride) on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate (3a) afforded a product, m.p. 140°. It was identified as 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-phenyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (4a) on the basis of chemical characteristics and ir, nmr and mass spectral analyses as well as by polarimetry. This reaction of 2 was also extended to several other aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (3) and corresponding products (4b-4g) were isolated.

Interaction of 1-phenyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (5a) and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (6) afforded a product, m.p. 121°. It was assigned the structure 1-phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (7a) by the usual chemical characteristics and ir, nmr and mass spectral analyses and also polarimetry. The reaction of 6 was also extended to other 1-aryl/(*H*)-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (5) and corresponding 2,4-isodithiobiurets (7b-7e) were isolated.

Experimental

The required aryl and alkyl isothiocyanates and 1-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides were prepared by the methods described earlier^{3,4}. 1 was prepared by the interaction of ammonia and 6. The latter

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

was prepared by the extension of earlier known method⁶ using lead thiocyanate in place of silver thiocyanate.

Preparation of 6: A solution of tetra-*O*-acetyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl bromide (5 g) in sodium-dried xylene (30 ml) was treated with lead thiocyanate (4 g). The mixture was refluxed gently for 3 h. The solution was then allowed to cool and filtered from the lead salt and treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (70 ml) with stirring. Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate was precipitated out as a white solid (3.5 g). The crude isothiocyanate was crystallised from ethanol-water, m.p. 112-114° (lit.⁶ 111-113°) (Found: C, 45.87; H, 4.32; N, 3.82; S, 8.44. $C_{15}H_{19}O_9NS$ calcd. for: C, 46.28; H, 4.88; N, 3.59; S, 8.22%).

Preparation of 2: A mixture of 1 (0.02 M, 8.1 g), benzyl chloride (0.02 M, 2.5 g) and ethanol (20 ml) were heated under gentle reflux for 90 min. The resulting acidic solution when rendered basic with dilute ammonium hydroxide yielded a granular solid 2 (8 g), crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 136° (Found: N, 5.61. $C_{22}H_{28}C_6N_2S$ calcd. for: N, 5.64%); gave a picrate, m.p. 104°.

Preparation of 4: 3a (0.01 M, 1.3 g) was added to a benzene solution of 2 (0.01 M, 4.9 g in 30 ml) and the mixture was refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 3 h. Then benzene was removed by distillation and the resulting syrup was triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol to afford a solid 4a (5 g) crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 140° (Found: C, 54.82; H, 5.31; N, 6.65; S, 10.92. $C_{22}H_{28}O_9N_2S_2$ calcd. for: C, 55.15; H, 5.22; N, 6.65; S, 10.14%); tlc (silica gel, EtOH-EtOAc (1:1) solvent) single spot (R_f 0.75); $[\alpha]_D^{25} -9.10$ (c 2.248 in $CHCl_3$); ν_{max} 3340 (NH), 1740 (C=O), 1580 (C=N), 1230 (S-Bz), 1040 (C=S) and 900 cm^{-1} (β -D-glucopyranose ring⁶⁻⁸). Its nmr spectra displayed signals due to δ 8.4 (NH), 7.35-7.45 (ArH)⁹, 2.02 (equatorial acetoxy protons¹⁰ indicating presence of β -anomer) and 4.95-5.32 ppm (lit.¹¹ 4.75-5.38; β -anomer); mass spectra did not show molecular ion peak.

The other compounds prepared were, 4b, 147°; 4c, 143°; 4d, 150°; 4e, 79°d; 4f, 62°d; 4g, 100°d.

Preparation of 7: 6 (0.02 M, 7.7 g) was added to a benzene solution of 5a (0.02 M, 4.8 g in 60 ml) and the mixture refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 6 h. The solvent was then distilled off. The resultant syrupy mass was then triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol to yield a white solid 7a (7 g) crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 121° (Found: C, 54.79; H, 5.22; N, 6.68; S, 9.89. $C_{29}H_{38}O_9N_2S_2$ calcd. for: C, 55.15; H, 5.22; N, 6.65; S, 10.14%); tlc (EtOH-EtOAc solvent) single spot (R_f 0.72); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +11.13$ (c 2.3276 in $CHCl_3$); ν_{max} 3420 (NH), 1740 (C=O), 1575 (C=N) and 900 cm^{-1} (β -anomer); δ 8.3 (NH), 7.15-7.35 (ArH), 2.12 (equatorial acetoxy protons) and 5.05-5.35 (β -anomer); mass spectrum did not show molecular ion peak.

The other compounds prepared were, 7b, 116°; 7c, 131°; 7d, 123°; and 7e, 136°.

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